

ITRN Biannual Strategic Plan 2023 - 2024

In line with ITRN's objectives, over the next two years, we aim to hold our position at the frontier of promoting open science with a researcher's perspective and a multidisciplinary approach. To this end, we intend to pursue certain lines of development aimed at strengthening our activities in the field of open science. We will follow two of the main **topics** that constitute the foundations of the ITRN activity: **Research policy and networking; Education and dissemination**. Our efforts will focus on a proposal that combines the enhancement of expertise, and the quality of activities through targeted planning. By leveraging these aspects, ITRN contributes to shaping the direction of higher education and research in a way that reflects open science principles as the basis of “good science”.

In line with the path of the past few years, the **activities** for the next two years will be developed along the following main lines of action:

1. Promoting reform of research evaluation;
2. Strengthening national institutional relationships;
3. Consolidating and developing joint actions with international institutions;
4. Expanding nodes and connections within the ITRN, by stimulating initiatives at a local level;
5. Outlining a targeted educational programme to promote relevant aspects of open research;
6. Rewarding open science practices.

The expected outcomes of the ITRN Strategic Plan are:

- the consolidation of a national association that positions Italy among the leaders in the field of open science at the international level;
- the support and the promotion of the development of an open science culture and “research evaluation reform” at the national level, in partnership with national and international actors;
- the dissemination of an advanced “educational” program focused on open science research with targeted actions for higher level education.

By achieving these outcomes, the ITRN Strategic Plan aims to foster a more inclusive and collaborative research ecosystem in Italy that embraces open science principles and practices. This will facilitate the production and dissemination of high-quality research.

☑ **Topic: Research policy and networking**

Activity 1: Promoting reform of research evaluation

Referent person(s): Davide Crepaldi, Carlo Miniussi

Synthetic objective: The goal is to promote a reform of research evaluation practices by defining and setting a common direction for change. This will involve rethinking how research, researchers, and research performing organisations are evaluated in order to better align with

contemporary needs and priorities. Ultimately, the objective of promoting research evaluation reform is to foster a more equitable and effective research ecosystem that better serves the needs of research and society at large.

Target: The primary targets of this effort are policy-makers, universities and research organisations, and scientific societies at the national level.

Actions / Planned activity

Opening an internal discussion about the status quo of the assessment and set up ideas on the matter.

Engaging in dialogue and consultation with targeted subjects to build a shared understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with research evaluation.

Participate in discussion groups (e.g., CoARA; ANVUR), to define and set a common direction for changes in the practice of evaluation of research, of researchers and of research performing organisations.

Redefining the criteria for evaluating research outputs (e.g., see [UKRN position on meta-research](#)), rethinking the role of metrics and indicators, and exploring alternative methods for assessing research impact and productivity in line with CoARA core commitments.

Encouraging the use of alternative metrics and indicators that better capture the full range of contributions made by researchers (and research organisations)

Advocating for changes in funding and reward policy that support the adoption of new evaluation practices (e.g., promote open science badges; work collaboratively with grant agencies).

Result: build broad-based support for reform to develop and implement effective strategies for a change in the evaluation system.

Reference period: annual actions from summer 2023 toward 2024 in synchrony with the relevant the CoARA and ANVUR scheduling.

Quantifiers: Producing a document that evaluates the current evaluation system and proposes (at least in the form of ideas) new evaluation criteria. Sitting in at least one of the CoARA working groups with an active role (e.g. by promoting ITRN lines of work), or having a leadership role in the CoARA National Chapter. Becoming a regular counterpart of ANVUR in the reform of research assessment (Menico Rizzi).

Activity 2: Strengthen national institutional relationships

Referent person(s): Carlo Miniussi, Massimo Grassi, Davide Crepaldi

Synthetic objective: The objective is to increase ITRN's influence and participation in decision-making bodies of institutions related to universities and research organisations (e.g., G7, scientific associations). The aim is to ensure that the perspectives of ITRN are considered and valued in the planning and implementation of future career and scientific investment choices.

Target: The primary targets of this objective are universities and research organisations; national scientific societies, grant maker institutions.

Actions / Planned activity:

Building stronger connections with policy-makers and investors at the national level to advocate for the interests of Open Science.

Participating in conferences, workshops, and other events to enhance visibility and engagement in the research and academic sectors.

Providing feedback and recommendations on relevant policies/initiatives to ensure that the interests promoted by ITRN are taken into account.

Developing and implementing effective communication strategies to raise awareness of ITRN goals, achievements, and contributions.

Result: By engaging in these activities, ITRN can build a stronger presence and influence in decision-making bodies associated with universities and research organisations.

Reference period: Annual actions from summer 2023 toward 2024 in synchrony with the national congresses and meetings of scientific associations.

Quantifiers: Number of dissemination events (i.e., talk, symposia, round tables, etc.) over the reference period.

Activity 3: Consolidating and developing joint actions with international institutions.

Referent person(s): Cristina Zogmaister, Massimo Grassi

Synthetic objective: Consolidating and developing joint actions with the Reproducibility Networks as well as with international institutions that practise and promote Open Science in research; the aim is to keep the activities of the network at an international level.

Target: international RN, EU institutions, international research organisations; Cochrane Collaboration

Actions / Planned activity:

Participation in events promoted by the various reproducibility networks

Participation in events of international research organisations (e.g., congresses, round tables)

Participation in European calls and round table about reproducibility

Result: By engaging in these activities ITRN will consolidate its international network and will set the basis for new ones. The complete submission for the Horizon Widera EO1 call will be a first pragmatic action as a result of this networking.

Reference period: Annual actions from summer 2023 toward 2024 in synchrony with online and in person meetings of the reproducibility networks, organisations or related to Horizon Widera EO1 plan (two members of ITRN are currently involved in this call).

Quantifiers: Participating regularly in the network-of-networks meetings; being part of at least one network that places a bid on a large-scale funding proposal on Open Science (e.g., WIDERA).

Activity 4: Expanding nodes and connections within the ITRN, by stimulating initiatives at a local level

Referent person(s): Ezia Rizzi, Tiziana Metitieri

Synthetic objective: Consolidating existing network. Create new contacts with individuals and/or research institutions. Broadening the spectrum of fields currently represented in the network.

Target: individuals (new members), regional nodes, Ambassadors in different scientific fields

Actions / Planned activity:

Create on site events with the institution (both in person or online). Promote the creation of events by members of the institution. Promote events within scientific meetings of various societies

Result: By engaging in these activities ITRN will consolidate its Italian network as well as it will create connections with new potential national partners.

Reference period: annual actions from summer 2023 toward 2024

Quantifiers: Getting to at least four local nodes; at least 50% of the nodes have promoted at least one local initiative.

🎯 **Topic: Education and dissemination**

Activity 5: Targeted educational programme to promote some relevant aspects of open research

Referent person(s): Cristina Zogmaister, Claudia Mazzuca

Synthetic objective: Define an educational programme to promote some relevant aspects of open research. We are aware that the use of open science practices requires the dissemination of open science ideas within the research community as well as within the general public, that in many cases is still unaware of these practices. The aim is to provide a basic education for scientists (in particular early research career ones) and to promote awareness in laypeople on open science practices.

Target: doctoral students, post docs, principal investigators; Italian Research Centers; national community; schools.

Actions / Planned activity: On Line Seminars, promotion of on site seminars; outreach activities targeted to a broad audience.

Result: Raise awareness on the not-so-healthy status of current research and research evaluation system, Increase the dissemination of the knowledge about open science and open science practices, increase the quality of the education.

Reference period: planning May 2023; annual actions 2023-2024.

Quantifiers: number of organised events; number of participants per event, overall number of "single person" participation (irrespective of how many times).

Activity 6: Rewarding open science practices

Referent person(s): Vittorio Iacovella, Dario Mangione, Ezia Rizzi, Claudia Mazzuca

Synthetic objective: As a collector of relevant Italian open-science related activities, an annual end of year prize will be awarded to a researcher (or institution) who has promoted, through various research or training actions, open science in Italy. In addition, one (or more) awards will

be possibly planned to support research activities of young researchers (e.g. travel grants; partial APC support).

Target: Researchers (at any level but in particular young ones) and institution currently part of the network

Actions / Planned activity:

Define a call/calls: ITRN Award, honorary membership, travel grants, support for APC.

Publicising the call before approaching the deadline with an email (mentioning past successful stories) sent to the whole local community;

Result: Rewarding open science practices should increase the adoption of the same practices.

Reference period: Define criteria before the annual ITRN meeting and award the prize during the same meeting

Quantifiers: Awarding the 2024 Prize for activities in the year 2023.

The ITRN Steering Committee